

Practitioner Notes for

I-SPI-K5

Indigenous - story prompted, illustrated - Kessler 5

Health practitioners often need to undertake some kind of measurement of an individual's mental health or social and emotional wellbeing as part of referral processes. While there are a number of surveys that have been developed for non Indigenous people, the direct questioning typical of surveys is often not familiar or comfortable for many Indigenous people. Indirect questioning is more typical in many Indigenous cultures in Australia; for example telling a story about an issue and waiting for a person to tell if that is also a 'true story' for them.

Another feature of surveys which many Indigenous people find difficult, is that they are usually 'text or talk only' with no accompanying visual context to help people better understand what is written or read aloud. Visual cues can help people better understand survey questions especially for the many Indigenous people who have hearing loss and/or literacy difficulties. Between 40% (urban areas) and 70% (remote areas) of Indigenous adults have some degree of hearing loss as a result of childhood ear disease.

Difficulties with surveys can be an obstacle to Indigenous people accessing mental health services. The I-SPI-K5 is one initiative to address this by adapting the Kessler 5 Psychological Distress Scale – a version of the Kessler scale already adapted for use with Indigenous people in Australia. The I-SPI-K5 is a story based and illustrated survey developed with input from a number of cultural consultants. They confirmed it was easier for people in their community to understand and respond to than the non adapted survey. The Kessler 5 questions are presented as a story about someone else with some clarifying information and an image. The clarifying information has been developed for the communities I work with after consultation with local Indigenous people. Such clarifying information may need to be adapted for what is easiest to understand in local communities by working with local cultural consultants. Local validation studies would also be desirable. As a 'self report' measure the provided information is only accurate if questions are clearly understood by those answering the survey. Non verbal responses can be an important indicator of understanding and practitioners need to consider knowledge of the person's whole context in considering the score responses from the K5. Of course culturally appropriate approaches to Indigenous mental health are holistic and strength oriented with a focus on social and emotional wellbeing as well as considering 'psychological distress'.

The I—SPI—K5 as a possible measure of psychological distress is shared as a practitioner adapted version of a well respected tool. Other practitioners, in conjunction with local cultural consultants, may like to consider its suitability for local Indigenous communities. Thanks to the many who have provided input, advice and/or support in its development to date. I would appreciate receiving any feedback on the survey and interest of any organisations who may wish to take part in any local validation studies.

Dr Damien Howard

Scoring

None of the time	=	1
Little of the time	=	2
Some of the time	=	3
Most of the time a lot	=	4
All the time	=	5

Add scores together

A score between 5-11 indicates a low/moderate level of psychological distress

A score between 12-25 indicates a high/very level of psychological distress

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